

WEAR RESISTANCE OF HIGH TEMPERATURE POLYMERS AND
COMPOSITES TESTED WITH A NEW SLIDING WEAR APPARATUS *

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INTRODUCTION

Many engineering composites are wear loaded caused by sliding counterparts, e.g. when being used as bushings or bearings. The material loss rate depends on the materials tested, the microscopical wear mechanisms and the environmental testing conditions [1-4].

A wear apparatus especially designed for the investigation of the wear behavior of neat and fiber reinforced polymers sliding against smooth metallic surfaces at different external temperatures was used for the study described here. Many important testing parameters could be varied according to different testing materials and requirements [5]:

- sliding speed v
- loading pressure p
- temperature of the counterpart T
- humidity
- gaseous environment
- roughness of the counterface

The wear determining values, coefficient of friction and specific wear rate \dot{w}_s , were calculated in regular time intervals Δt using the measured torque M and the height reduction Δh :

$$\dot{w}_s = (\Delta h / \Delta t) * (1 / p * v)$$

$$\mu = F_p / F_{\text{frict.}} = (F_p * d / 2) / M$$

where F_p = loading force; d = disc diameter; M = measured torque
A standardized pin-on-disc configuration was used as the heart of the machine. It allowed the variation of many testing conditions and a computerized data collection. Running-in periods could be separated from the steady-state wear without manual operations. This lead to higher accuracy and more efficient machine usage.

*The paper is dedicated to the 60.birthday of Professor H.J.Sinn
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Figure 1. Schematical pin-on-disc test configuration

EXPERIMENTAL

All the tests were performed on a unique pin-on-disc tribometer (Figure 1). A test pin (D) of about 3 x 4 mm was fixed in the sample holder (G), and slid against a 100 Cr6 (German standard DIN 616) steel ring (E) (80 mm in inner and 108 mm in outer diameter). The average roughness at the beginning of the test was about 0.25-0.4 μm and the hardness was measured as 63 HRC. The test pin rotated at constant velocities of 1.0 and 3.3 m/s, respectively, and the applied pressures were 1 MPa or 2 MPa. An unused disc track was selected for each test specimen. Test temperatures in a range between room temperature to 220 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, were reached by using an electric heater (F) which set just underneath the steel disc. The torque generated at the pin disc interface was monitored by the torque measuring system (H), and the reduction of the test-pin length was measured by a linear voltage displacement transducer (I). All measured data were digitalized and stored in a personal computer system.

A typical plot of all values measured vs time is shown in Figure 2. Sliding procedure would not start until the heating expansion of the specimen had stopped. Then, the test pin continuously rotated for at least a period of 5 hours. During these 5 hours, every 5 seconds in the first 30 minutes of sliding (and every 30 seconds for the rest of time) the record system picked up a signal from the measuring elements.

The materials tested with this new apparatus were different high temperature resistant polymers with or without different forms of lubricants and fiber reinforcements.

Figure 2. Measured data of a complete experiment

RESULTS

Most of the friction and wear data generated from our tests are shown in Figure 3. A clear reduction of the wear rate caused by addition of short or woven carbon fibers to a thermoplastic polyetheretherketone (PEEK) matrix is visible. Further reduction in \dot{w}_s occurred by the addition of 10 wt% PTFE. It lead to a wear reducing transfer film on the metallic counterpart. Graphite acted as a filler for building a surface lubricant that was still efficient at elevated temperatures.

The influence of different graphite contents was investigated for the polyimide system. Adding 15 wt% graphite lead to lower values at room temperature and 220°C. An increase to 40 wt% shows a slight decrease only at 220 °C and an additional fluorocarbon content is almost of no influence.

At 220 °C a lower coefficient of friction but a higher specific wear rate was found for almost all materials in general. Carbon fibers caused an increase of the coefficient of friction and the transfer film of the PTFE and graphite filler material lead to very low coefficients. The same is visible for the polyimide system where the coefficient of friction was decreased by an increasing graphite content .

As there is a clear temperature dependance of the wear properties the testing temperature was varied more systematically for one particular material combination. The curves of the carbon fiber, PTFE and graphite filled PEEK show then a minimum in the coefficient of friction and the wear rate in a temperature range around 100 °C(Figure 4).

Figure 3. Wear data determined at 20 °C and 220 °C
 $v = 3.3$ m/s, $p = 2$ MPa

The wear behavior of unfilled PEEK has been studied by other investigators [6,7] who also found a similar trend as a function of testing temperature. It is supposed that the minimum here is a result of two effects, 1.) a weakening of the matrix when the temperature in the contact zone approaches its glass transition temperature (favourable for the formation of a transfer film), 2.) due to the first effect, an improved efficiency of the internal lubricants (PTFE, graphite). The increase in wear rate with further temperature enhancement is explained by a simultaneous effect of easier removal of the weakened matrix material and the filler and reinforcing components.

Figure 4. Temperature dependence of the wear data

CONCLUSIONS

In studying of the results generated from the tests it is suggested that there is no material that exhibits an overall favourable behavior. PEEK filled with 10 wt% PTFE, 10 wt% Graphite and 10 % CF shows the best average properties, followed by the graphite filled polyimide. Further advantages of the thermoplastic PEEK system are its processibility by injection molding and the 3 - 4 fold higher fracture toughness when compared the rather brittle thermoset polyimide.

It is important to note that in general the experimental values must be determined under the same conditions as those found in the practical application. Otherwise the data will not be applicable and a transformation of a ranking order of materials evaluated to other conditions is only restricted possible. The new designed wear apparatus allows the variation of T, p and v in a broad range and the measured data are in good agreement with those given by other authors [8,9]. A prediction of the wear behavior for materials including different fillers is impossible, unless the complex interactions are investigated in more detail.

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